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ASSESSMENT OF INDIGENOUS AND MODERN AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES TO ENHANCE FOOD SECURITY IN MUBI NORTH L.G.A., ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study assessed indigenous and modern agricultural practices to enhance food security in Mubi North LGA, Adamawa State Nigeria. The objectives included identifying potential barriers and opportunities for integrating indigenous farming knowledge with modern agricultural practices to enhance regional food security in study area and identifying the contributions of indigenous farming knowledge to income generation among farmers in the area. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were collected through structured questionnaires and interviews of randomly selected 135 farmers and 15 agricultural officials in Mubi North LGA of Adamawa State. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics for research questions while hypothesis was tested using t-test analysis. Findings reveal that economic pressures, market forces, perceived inefficiency, government policies, and social perceptions are primary factors affecting the adoption of indigenous practices. Farmers perceive that adopting these methods supports and enhanced food security underscoring their potential for financial stability. However, analysis of yield outcomes shows no significant difference between adopters and non-adopters, suggesting that with access to larger farmlands, adopters could achieve similar or better yields ($p < 0.05$). The study concludes that integrating traditional knowledge with modern techniques can strengthen agricultural resilience, with recommendations for government support in training, improved market access, and collaboration among stakeholders to foster sustainable practices.*

Keywords: Indigenous agricultural practices, food security, barriers and opportunities, farm yield

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, ensuring food security has been a central focus of global agricultural policies, with sustainable practices promoted as essential for meeting the needs of a growing population. Globally, the integration of diverse agricultural practices is proposed as a critical

strategy for enhancing food security and building resilience against climate variability. Research has shown that indigenous agricultural knowledge systems, which are often finely tuned to local environments, offer effective, sustainable strategies that have enabled communities to maintain agricultural productivity over centuries (FAO, 2020;

Nyong, 2019). However, while indigenous practices offer unique benefits, integrating them with modern agricultural techniques presents both opportunities and challenges. Differences in scale, technology, and environmental priorities necessitate careful management to ensure both approaches' benefits are fully harnessed (Altieri & Nicholls, 2020; Ocheni et al., 2019).

In Nigeria, food security remains a priority as the country faces challenges from land degradation, limited access to modern agricultural resources, and climate variability—all of which threaten food production (Odeyemi & Ogunmola, 2020). Indigenous farming methods continue to be widely practiced, contributing to enhanced crop diversity, soil fertility, and resilience against environmental challenges (Ajani & Olayemi, 2020). Yet, the adoption of modern agricultural practices often clashes with indigenous techniques, resulting in an underutilization of valuable local knowledge that could complement mechanized agriculture. National policies have increasingly acknowledged the importance of integrating indigenous knowledge into agricultural development initiatives to achieve food security, boost crop yields, and improve farmers' income (Akinola & Olorunfemi, 2019).

At the regional level, Adamawa State in North-East Nigeria faces particular food security and income generation challenges, especially in Mubi North LGA, where farming practices remain deeply rooted in indigenous knowledge systems. This area, characterized by unique environmental conditions and expertise in local farming techniques, presents significant potential for a productive blend of indigenous and modern agricultural practices (Aliyu et al., 2020). However, farmers in Mubi North often

face barriers such as limited access to modern technology, inadequate infrastructure, and scarce financial resources, which hinder such integration (Umaru et al., 2020). Despite these challenges, combining indigenous and modern farming practices offers unique opportunities for improved food security and increased income generation through enhanced productivity and resilience.

This research aims to provide insights into the specific barriers and opportunities that farmers in Mubi North LGA encounter in merging traditional and modern agricultural practices. It also seeks to examine the contributions of indigenous knowledge to food security and income generation, with the broader goal of supporting policy development that fosters sustainable agricultural practices in the region.

Indigenous knowledge refers to the traditional practices, beliefs and innovations of local communities, often passed down through generations. In agriculture, indigenous knowledge encompasses traditional farming techniques, crop selection and soil management practices while modern agricultural practices refer to the use of advanced technology, science and innovative methods to improve crop yields, quality and sustainability. Some example of modern agricultural practices includes: precision farming, sustainable agriculture, innovative farming techniques, digital agriculture and mechanized agriculture

However, despite the growing recognition of indigenous farming knowledge as a valuable resource for sustainable agriculture, rural farmers in Mubi North Local Government Area (LGA), Adamawa State, face numerous obstacles in integrating traditional practices with modern agricultural methods. While indigenous knowledge has historically

supported resilience in agriculture by fostering sustainable use of local resources, biodiversity, and environmental conservation, the increasing influence of modern, industrialized farming practices has led to a decline in the use and appreciation of these traditional techniques. This shift has contributed to a reliance on imported inputs and mechanized techniques that may not align with local environmental conditions, potentially undermining food security and ecological balance in the region.

Moreover, there is limited empirical understanding of the specific barriers and opportunities in blending indigenous and modern agricultural practices to address food security in Mubi North LGA. Existing studies emphasize the benefits of both approaches individually—indigenous practices in enhancing soil fertility and pest management and modern techniques in improving productivity and efficiency. However, there remains a gap in research on how these practices can be harmonized effectively to enhance food security in the unique context of Mubi North. This knowledge gap impedes the development of agricultural policies and interventions tailored to the region's specific socio-economic and environmental conditions.

Another challenge lies in the gradual erosion of indigenous knowledge among younger generations, who may perceive modern agriculture as more advanced and overlook the potential benefits of traditional practices. Without targeted efforts to foster intergenerational knowledge transfer and facilitate a cohesive integration of these methods, the region risks losing invaluable indigenous techniques that contribute to long-term sustainability, resilience, and local food security. Therefore, it is essential to investigate both the barriers that hinder and the opportunities that enable the integration of

indigenous and modern agricultural practices in Mubi North LGA. By exploring this integration, the study aims to provide insights that can inform sustainable agricultural practices, enhance food security, and support policy initiatives that respect and incorporate indigenous knowledge alongside modern advancements for a more resilient agricultural system in the region. The specific objectives of the study are to: (1) identify potential barriers and opportunities for integrating indigenous farming knowledge with modern agricultural practices to enhance regional food security in Mubi North LGA, Adamawa State and (2) identify the contributions of indigenous farming knowledge in the study area, toward income generation among farmers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The study was carried out in Mubi North Local Government Area, Adamawa State, North-eastern Nigeria. The local government has over 45 villages (Adebayo, 2004), with numerous farms. It has a population of about 175,165 people (National Population Census, 2006) spread over 11 political wards. It lies on the west bank of the river Yedseram (a stream that flow north into Lake Chad) and on the western flank at the foot of the Mandara mountain.

Mubi North Local Government Area covers a land mass of about 752.85km² (Adebayo, 2004). It is one of the twenty-one Local Government Area of Adamawa State and lies between latitude 9⁰26'1" and latitude 10⁰10'1" N and between longitude 13⁰11'00" and 13⁰44'01" E (ministry of land and survey Yola, Adamawa state). The entire town and its environs bordered with Maiha Local Government area on the south, Hong Local Government on the west, Michika Local

TYPES AND SOURCES OF DATA

The data for the study were derived from both real-time and historical sources. Real-time data were collected directly by the researcher through surveys, interviews, and observations aimed at addressing the research problem. This data was obtained via structured questionnaires distributed to selected farmers, as well as through interviews with officials from the State Ministry of Agriculture, the Adamawa Agricultural Development Programme (AADP), and the Fadama Group. Past data consist of secondary information sourced from existing literature, including government publications and organizational records. Reports, books, and unpublished works from AADP, Fadama, and the Ministry of Agriculture was able to enrich the analysis by providing background and context.

DATA COLLECTION

The study targets a population of 3,459 farmers in Mubi North LGA, Adamawa State. From this population, a sample size of 364 individuals were selected, including 346 farmers and 18 officials from agricultural extension services and the Agricultural Development Programme (ADP). The sample size for farmers has been calculated using Cochran's formula to ensure accuracy and representativeness. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire divided into sections for personal information and research-related questions, complemented by an interview guide. To measure respondents' perceptions, a Likert scale was employed, allowing for an in-

depth understanding of attitudes and experiences. Data collection was conducted by research assistants familiar with the region, who will administer questionnaires, conduct interviews, and observe farming practices to capture a broad perspective on agricultural methods.

DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive statistics were done to summarize the data, while regression analysis was done to test the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. Responses on the Likert scale was analyzed using weighted mean scores to ensure clarity in the interpretation of perceptions. Hypotheses were rejected if the p-value is less than 0.05, and a weighted mean score above 2.5 were indicate agreement with the survey items, providing a clear framework for evaluating responses.

The following hypothesis was set for the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the Mean Yield per Hectare (Kg/hect) for Adopters and Non-Adopters Farmers in Mubi North LGA, Adamawa State Based on Level of Adoption

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

Table 1: Perception of Farmers on Potential of Barriers toward Integrating Indigenous Farming Knowledge with Modern Agricultural Practices to Enhance Regional Food Security in Mubi North LGA

Items	Frequency	Percentage	Rank Order
Lack of Awareness	165	9.2	8
Perceived Inefficiency	231	12.9	3
Labour Intensity	192	10.7	6
Limited Access to Resources	33	1.8	10
Economic Pressures	291	16.2	1
Cultural Shift	167	9.3	7
Government Policies and Incentives	205	11.4	4
Market Forces	256	14.2	2
Climate Change	56	3.1	9
Perception of Prestige	201	11.2	5
Total	1797*		

*Multiple Responses

The results presented in Table 1 highlight the primary barriers to integrating indigenous farming knowledge with modern agricultural practices aimed at enhancing regional food security in Mubi North LGA. Economic pressures emerged as the most significant factor limiting the adoption of indigenous farming practices, accounting for 16.1% of the total factors (ranked 1st). This is followed by market forces, which constitute 14.2% of the limiting factors (ranked 2nd). Perceived inefficiency of indigenous farming practices is the third most significant barrier, contributing 12.9% to the total factors.

Government policies and incentives are ranked 4th, representing 11.4% of the barriers, while the perception of prestige is ranked 5th, accounting for 11.2% of the factors. Additionally, lack of awareness, climate change, and limited access to resources were ranked 8th, 9th, and 10th, respectively. These findings indicate that economic pressures, market forces, perceived inefficiency, government policies and incentives, and perceptions of prestige are the primary factors affecting the adoption of indigenous farming practices in the study area. Addressing these issues may be crucial for fostering the integration of traditional knowledge with modern agricultural methods to improve food security.

Figure 2: Potential Benefits of Integrating Indigenous Farming Practices with Modern
Source: Author 2024

Agricultural Methods for Enhancing Productivity and Sustainability

The findings depicted in Figure 2 illustrate the five-point rating scale used by farmers to evaluate the potential benefits of integrating

indigenous farming practices with modern agricultural methods for enhancing productivity and sustainability. The results show mean values of 3.0 and above for all the identified benefits, reflecting a general acceptance and positive outlook among the farmers regarding each potential benefit.

Table 2: Perception of Farmers on Contributions of Indigenous Farming Knowledge toward Income Generation in Mubi North LGA, Adamawa State

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
Farming that base strictly on indigenous practices can generate enough produce that farmers bring to market after meeting household needs	1.69	0.34	Disagree
Like mechanized farming, the indigenous farming practices could also attract special sales offers	3.42	0.16	Agree
There are some marketers that specifically look for farming produce through indigenous practices	3.23	0.27	Agree
Adopting traditional farming system could make farmer product become more attractive in the market	3.17	0.09	Agree
Peoples are specially look for farm produce grown using indigenous farming practices	3.99	0.15	Agree
Grand Mean	3.10		Agree

The results on Table 2 reveals the respective perception of farmers on contributions of indigenous farming knowledge toward income generation in Mubi North LGA, Adamawa State. The results show that most farmers disagreed to the assertion that farming that base strictly on indigenous practices can generate enough produce that farmers bring to market after meeting household needs (mean =1.69, standard deviation =0.34). Also, most farmers agreed that indigenous faming could attract special sales offers like mechanized farming (mean=3.42; standard deviation =0.16). Meanwhile, farmers strongly agreed that there are some marketers that specifically look for

farming produce through indigenous practices (mean =3.23; Standard deviation =0.27). Likewise, farmers expressed their agreement view to the assertion that adopting traditional farming system could make farmer product become more attractive in the market (mean =3.17; Standard deviation =0.09). Respondents disagreed to the statement that peoples are specially look for farm produce grown using indigenous farming practices (Mena =3.99, Standard Deviation =0.15). The grand mean value of 3.10, which surpasses the neutral midpoint of 3.0 on the five-point scale, indicates that, on average, farmers agree that adopting indigenous farming practices can

generate income for their households. This positive perception underscores the potential of traditional agricultural methods to contribute to the financial stability and economic well-being of farming families.

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

Table 3 presents the result of the test of significance between the Mean Yield per Hectare (Kg/hect) for Adopters and Non-Adopters Farmers in Mubi North LGA, Adamawa State Based on Level of Adoption.

Table 3: T-test Analysis of Difference in Mean Yield per Hectare (Kg/hect) for Adopters and Non-Adopters Farmers in Mubi North LGA, Adamawa State Based on Level of Adoption

Category of Farmers	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
IFK Adopters	63	37.440	6.9894	.8806	1.033	336	.067
Non-IFK Adopters	275	35.585	6.4246	.3874			

The consideration of farm size in respect to the farm yield (kg/hect) for both adopters and non-adopters of indigenous farming practices were subjected to t-test analysis. The results, as shown in Table 3, revealed a t-test value of 1.033 with a degree of freedom of 337 and a p-value of 0.067. Since the calculated p-value of 0.067 is greater than the hypothetical p-value of 0.05, this indicates a non-statistically significant difference between the mean yield per hectare of the two groups. Specifically, the mean yields of 37.440 kg/hect was recorded for adopters which is slightly but non-significantly higher than mean yield per hectare of 35.585kg/hect for non-adopters. This suggests that both adopters of indigenous farming recorded and non-adopters recorded similar yield per hectare. These findings indicate that farmers who have adopted indigenous farming practices could have recorded similar or better mean farm output per hectare than non-adopters if secure larger farmland. The findings reinforce the

understanding that adopting indigenous farming practices does not inherently diminish farm output. However, it has been observed that farmers who utilize these traditional methods often work on smaller plots of land. This tendency is largely due to the labour-intensive nature of indigenous farming techniques, which require significant manual effort, making it difficult to manage larger areas efficiently. Additionally, the lack of scalability in these practices poses another challenge; expanding farm size without compromising productivity is often impractical.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings first research question indicates that economic pressures, market forces, perceived inefficiency, government policies and incentives, and perceptions of prestige are the primary factors affecting the adoption of indigenous farming practices in the study area.

Addressing these issues may be crucial for fostering the integration of traditional knowledge with modern agricultural methods to improve food security. Aliyu et al. (2020) highlighted that economic constraints significantly hinder the adoption of indigenous farming practices. Farmers, grappling with financial difficulties, often turn to alternative methods that promise quicker yields to alleviate their immediate economic pressures. Indigenous farming systems are frequently perceived as less efficient and yielding lower returns, which leads farmers to abandon these traditional methods in favour of practices that offer more immediate financial relief. Also, Tabuti et al (2012) noted that the dynamics of local and global markets also influence adoption of indigenous practices. Market forces, including fluctuating prices, demand for products, and competition with cheaper, mass-produced alternatives, can deter farmers from adopting indigenous methods. If traditional practices do not align with market demands or are perceived as less competitive, farmers might be reluctant to integrate them. In the study by Adesina et al. (2019), it was found that there is a widespread perception that indigenous farming practices are less efficient compared to modern agricultural methods. This perception likely stem from a lack of familiarity with the benefits of traditional techniques or a belief that modern methods offer higher yields and better resource management. Nyong (2019) observed that overcoming various misconceptions about indigenous farming practices is crucial for integrating with other alternative farming.

The finding by Ajani and Olayemi (2020) pointed out that the role of government policies and incentives is significant in the adoption of indigenous farming technique. Those, inadequate support, lack of subsidies, or policies favouring modern farming

methods are hindering the adoption of indigenous practices among farmers. Aliyu et al. (2020) argued that the effective government intervention is needed to create an environment that supports and encourages the use of traditional methods, potentially through subsidies, grants, or research funding. Boza et al. (2020) established that social and cultural perceptions play a role toward the adoption of indigenous practices. Thus, indigenous farming methods has been viewed by many as outdated or less prestigious compared to modern, technologically advanced practices. This perception further influence farmers' willingness to adopt these methods, as they are simply seeking to align themselves with more contemporary or prestigious practices to enhance their social standing or market appeal.

The findings from the second research question indicate that, on average, farmers believe that adopting indigenous farming practices contributes to household income generation. This positive perception highlights the potential of traditional agricultural methods to support financial stability for farming families. Margwa (2020) found that farmers in Plateau State, Nigeria, recognize that indigenous practices, which emphasize sustainability and local resource use, can lower costs and boost productivity. Techniques like crop rotation, organic fertilization, and natural pest management reduce dependence on costly chemical inputs, which lowers production costs. Additionally, locally adapted crop varieties enhance yield stability, further contributing to household income (Ocheni et al., 2019). These crop varieties, naturally resilient to local climatic conditions, pests, and diseases, lead to more reliable harvests, essential for smallholder farmers who rely on their crops for sustenance and income. Nyong (2019) noted that, by securing their crops against environmental fluctuations, farmers in

Sub-Saharan Africa reduce the risk of crop failure, ensuring a more stable income.

While these practices support household financial needs, the quantity of surplus produce available for sale is often limited after meeting household consumption needs (Aliyu et al., 2020). This constraint suggests that, although indigenous methods contribute to household income, they may not yield enough surplus for substantial economic gains beyond the family unit. Adesina et al. (2019) found that indigenous farming in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, is often labor-intensive, limiting scalability compared to modern techniques. Nyong (2019) observed that indigenous farming's reliance on hand planting, manual weeding, and traditional tools limits farmers' capacity to expand cultivation without significantly increasing labor input, creating a barrier to large-scale production.

In many rural communities, the availability of labor is limited, and hiring additional labor is costly, further limiting indigenous farming scalability (Odeyemi & Ogunmola, 2020). Boza et al. (2020) observed that traditional practices, while effective, are labor-intensive, reducing overall production efficiency and limiting the ability to cultivate larger land areas. Nyong (2019) found that indigenous practices like shifting cultivation require specific land management approaches that may not be feasible for expansion due to community land ownership constraints and environmental degradation. Resource-intensive techniques, such as organic fertilization, are also challenging to manage at larger scales, potentially diluting their benefits.

Consequently, indigenous methods yield lower production volumes compared to modern intensive techniques, affecting the availability of marketable surplus (Francis, 2018).

Indigenous farming typically focuses on meeting household needs, with limited resources dedicated to commercial production (Nyong, 2019). Giulio (2018) suggested that addressing the challenges of scaling up indigenous farming requires integrating complementary modern techniques to increase productivity while preserving sustainability. For example, Ajani and Olayemi (2020) highlighted the need for government investment in infrastructure and market linkages to enhance surplus sale opportunities. Developing value-added products, such as jams from surplus fruits or dried vegetables, can also increase profitability. Thus, farmers largely agree that indigenous practices support household income, concerns regarding marketable surplus highlight the need for interventions to boost economic viability. Addressing scale, resource access, and infrastructure is essential for maximizing indigenous farming's income-generating potential and enhancing regional economic stability.

The finding from hypothesis established non-significant difference between yield by adopter farmers and non-adopter farmers. These findings indicate that farmers who have adopted indigenous farming practices could have recorded similar or better mean farm output per hectare than non-adopters if secure larger farmland. The findings reinforce the understanding that adopting indigenous farming practices does not inherently diminish farm output. However, it has been observed that farmers who utilize these traditional methods often work on smaller plots of land. This tendency is largely due to the labour-intensive nature of indigenous farming techniques, which require significant manual effort, making it difficult to manage larger areas efficiently. Additionally, the lack of scalability in these practices poses another

challenge; expanding farm size without compromising productivity is often impractical.

Altieri and Nicholls (2020) noted that constraints of indigenous farming methods—such as the reliance on manual labour and traditional tools—limit the ability to increase the scale of operations. Unlike modern farming techniques that benefit from mechanization and advanced technologies, indigenous practices are rooted in manual processes that demand more time and effort per unit of land. This makes it difficult for farmers to maintain larger farms without substantial increases in labour, which is not always feasible or cost-effective (Umaru et al., 2020).

Moreover, the non-scalability of these practices means that while they may be sustainable and effective on a smaller scale, they do not easily adapt to larger farming operations where the efficiency of labour and resource use becomes critical. Consequently, while indigenous farming practices remain valuable for certain types of agriculture, especially in preserving local knowledge and sustainable practices, their limitations in labour requirements and scalability often restrict the overall farm output for those who rely on them exclusively. Altieri and Nicholls (2020) noted that constraints of indigenous farming methods—such as the reliance on manual labour and traditional tools—limit the ability to increase the scale of operations. Unlike modern farming techniques that benefit from mechanization and advanced technologies, indigenous practices are rooted in manual processes that demand more time and effort per unit of land. This makes it difficult for farmers to maintain larger farms without substantial increases in labour, which is not always feasible or cost-effective (Umaru et al., 2020).

Moreover, the non-scalability of these practices means that while they may be sustainable and effective on a smaller scale, they do not easily adapt to larger farming operations where the efficiency of labour and resource use becomes critical. Consequently, while indigenous farming practices remain valuable for certain types of agriculture, especially in preserving local knowledge and sustainable practices, their limitations in labour requirements and scalability often restrict the overall farm output for those who rely on them exclusively

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study assessed highlights both the complexities and the economic potential of indigenous and modern farming practices in Mubi North LGA, Adamawa State. Findings from the first research question underscore the influence of economic pressures, market forces, perceived inefficiencies, government policies, and social perceptions of prestige on the adoption of indigenous farming methods. These factors shape farmers' decisions and indicate that, while indigenous practices are valued, external pressures and incentives also significantly affect their adoption.

The second research question's results reveal that farmers generally perceive indigenous farming practices as beneficial for household income generation, supporting economic stability. This positive outlook suggests that traditional agricultural methods can effectively complement modern approaches in fostering financial resilience among farming families. However, the findings from the hypothesis test show no significant difference in crop yields between adopters and non-adopters of indigenous practices, suggesting that while indigenous methods may have financial benefits, their yield outcomes are comparable

to those of more modern techniques in this region.

Overall, this study emphasizes the need to address economic and policy barriers to facilitate a more integrated approach, combining indigenous and modern practices to optimize both income potential and yield stability. Promoting supportive policies, accessible market linkages, and education on the long-term benefits of traditional practices could further strengthen indigenous farming's role in sustainable food security and economic stability in Mubi North LGA

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RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The Adamawa State government should initiate workshops to educate farmers on the benefits of indigenous practices, promoting sustainable agricultural adoption within the community.
- ii. The Ministry of Agriculture should invest in improving traditional food storage systems, extending shelf life and ensuring food quality for better yield reliability.

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